

ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF THE CREDIT-MODULE SYSTEM ON THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION AND THE FORMATION OF INDEPENDENT LEARNING SKILLS IN STUDENTS

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Relevance: The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-4884 dated November 6, 2020, established the introduction of a credit-module system in higher education and its gradual implementation in practice. This system is formed in accordance with international educational standards, in which students will have the opportunity to independently plan their educational paths, develop their interest in science, and acquire independent research skills. This plays an important role in preparing modern knowledge-capable, independent-thinking and initiative-taking specialists. Large-scale reforms are also being carried out in our republic to reform the higher education system, update its content and essence in line with the requirements of the times, and improve the quality of education, and the introduction of this system is recognized as one of the important stages in this direction.

Purpose: To determine and assess the impact of the credit-module system on the quality of education and the development of independent learning skills in students. The objectives of the work are to study the theoretical foundations of the credit-module system, analyze the practice of implementing the system at the Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute and its advantages, determine the role of the credit-module system in the process of forming independent learning skills, evaluate the effectiveness of the system based on empirical data and draw conclusions.

Methods: In order to assess the impact of the credit-module system on the quality of education, practical observations and social surveys were conducted at the Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute during the 2024-2025 academic year. The research mainly studied the opinions of students and professors, the level of application of the credit-module system in the educational process, students' attitude to independent learning, and the effectiveness of the system.

Results: According to students, the advantages of the credit-module system are highly appreciated by students in terms of developing independent learning, increasing the transparency of education, and openness to digital opportunities. As for the amount of time students devote to independent learning, more than half of them devote 6-15 hours a week to independent learning. This indicates that the credit-module system encourages self-management. The effectiveness of the credit-module system, according to professors, shows that professors also support the module system, especially emphasizing its positive effect on increasing student independence.

Conclusions: The results of practical research and surveys have shown that the credit-module system is an effective tool for improving the quality of education. Students are becoming more active in independent learning, their self-management skills are improving, and the transparency of the assessment process is increasing. At the same time, there is a need to expand methodological resources, improve the skills of teachers, and make wider use of digital tools for further development of the system. Based on practical analysis and statistical data, it can be noted that as a result of the introduction of the credit-module system into the higher education process:

- Students are developing skills such as independent learning, task planning, responsibility, and initiative.
- Transparency of assessment, effective use of digital educational tools, and an interactive approach are contributing to the improvement of the quality of education.
- In order to fully adapt to the system, it is necessary to strengthen the methodological and technical base in some areas.

The credit-module system serves not only to improve the quality of education, but also to form students as intellectually and professionally independent individuals.